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ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF FABRICS FROM CHEMICAL FIBERS IN A NATIONAL ECONOMY

Annotation: *A present article deals with and tries to analyze performance properties of fabrics made from chemical fibers and carried out a survey to find out optimal consumer properties used in a daily life. In accordance with the objectives of the study, the theoretical material of the influence of synthetic fabrics on human health has been studied, a social survey was conducted to get a closer insight on the popular choice of fabrics.*

Keywords: *chemical fibers, fabrics, synthetics, viscose, mixed materials, technology*

The application of chemical fibers in the creation of comfortable textiles to meet the growing needs of the population is a vital issue globally.

It has been historically predisposed that many fabrics, along with obvious advantages, have a set of serious disadvantages: migration of chemicals, high electrification, low hygroscopicity, increased thermal conductivity. Recently, such a concept as "eco-friendly clothing" has become quite common and popular. Interest in eco-friendly fabrics in our republic is not as high as, say in Europe, but it is only a matter of time. Many Internet users are interested in an ecological lifestyle, but on the topic of eco-textiles, they are still in a complete information vacuum. The results of this study will hopefully help fill this gap.

The purpose of the present work is to analyze the properties of fabrics made from chemical fibers, and to conduct a survey to determine the optimal consumer properties used in everyday life. In accordance with the objectives of the study, the following tasks were set and solved:

- studied the theoretical material of the influence of synthetic fabrics on human health;
- a social survey was conducted to study the opinion of the population regarding the choice of fabrics;
- found statistical data on the preferences for the use of chemical (blended) fabrics;
- the advantages and disadvantages of chemical (blended) fabrics are determined.

However, despite the disadvantages of artificial fibers, they also have clear advantages of their own. Textile products of a new generation meet human needs, have multifunctional and comfortable properties. The use of clothing based on synthetic fibers allows you to increase the performance of a human body in extreme conditions. Another advantage of artificial fibers is that their production would solve the problem with deficit of materials. Clothing businesses are not necessarily located near cotton plantations or livestock farms. Also, synthetic fabrics retain their shape well, do not wrinkle and do not shrink. It is namely these properties that are especially valued in everyday life and prompted the creation of mixed fabrics. With a mixture of chemical fibers, about 20% cotton, 5% linen,

81% wool and more than 97% silk fabrics are produced, which to a certain extent reduces the tension in providing the industry with raw materials and makes clothing more hygienic compared to purely synthetic material.

The traditional types of fibers based on cellulose raw materials are viscose and acetate fibers and threads. The output of viscose staple fibers is gradually increasing and is set to increase steadily. The technology for obtaining [1] these fibers has been established, however, it needs further development, especially in terms of expanding the range of fibers and their consumer properties, as well as reducing energy costs in solvent recycling processes. Therefore, the development of the production of lyocell fibers is slow, and yet they have a certain perspective.

In the current structure of staple fibers, natural fibers remain an undisputed favorite: their share in the world market in 2016 was 55% (synthetic - 34% and cellulose - 11%), but the leading positions are gradually lost, given that in 1970 their share exceeded 80% of the global market. The general trend in the structure is obvious - the predominant role of chemical staple fibers due to the uselessness of expanding agro-cultivated lands, price advantages, improved properties, and a more efficient technical and economic scale as a whole. In 2016, the development of textile raw materials was observed in three large countries producers, which account for more than 60% of the produced volume of fibers: in China, the increase happend due to chemical fibers; in India, all segments of the industry have grown, while in the United States, there is still an undulating dynamics that does not affect only the cotton harvest[2].

We have compiled a questionnaire to study the general opinion regarding the choice of fabrics. The purpose of the questionnaire is to find out whether the consumer always has a reasonable approach to the choice of fabric. The survey involved two groups of different age categories: young people (20-30 years old) and older people of elder age group(35-60 years old). The results of the social survey are shown in the table below.

The results of a social survey of the population of different age categories

Questions	Answer choices	Respondents aged 20-30; 20 persons	Respondents aged 35-60 20 person
1. Do you think that synthetic fabrics are harmful to human health?	yes no may be harmful	90%; 5%; 5%	74% 14% 12%
2. In your opinion, is the composition of the fabric indicated on the product label always correct?	yes no cannot tell the difference	75% 22%; 3%	46% 46% 8%
3. When choosing clothes,	yes	85%;	95%

are you interested in the composition of the fabric from which it is made?	no never thought of it	13%; 2%	5% -
4. Imagine the situation: You really liked the model of clothes, but the fabric is synthetic. Would you mind buying it?	yes no a suspicion may arise	60%; 25%; 15%.	60% 14% 26%
5. Do you think that if the underwear is made of natural fabric, then the composition of the fabric of the dress can be ignored?	yes no difficult to say does not matter	45%; 45%; 5%; 5%	27% 66% - 7%
6. Do you prefer natural fabric underwear?	yes no it must be nice depends on it price and my financial situation	80%; - 15% 5%	69% 3 - 28%

The survey showed that young people do not always choose fabrics wisely, due to a lack of life experience. They mostly value clothes made of chemical fibers in appearance and modern styles.

Adults rely on their life experience in assessing the physical and mechanical properties, color and performance properties of clothing made from synthetic and natural fabrics.

Most of the consumers pay attention to the quality of the fabric, as well as its cost. The main thing is that the clothes purchased meet the requirements of modern fashion, fit a body of a person, and of course the color quality is at the required level.

Maintaining these qualities in natural fiber fabrics has been difficult. Currently, the chemical and textile industries have consumer goods that combine the above qualities with the use of textile and knitted materials made from a mixture of chemical and natural fibers.

The majority of the population does not have the financial opportunity to purchase clothing made from natural fibers. The main factors in choosing clothes are still fashionable style, good fit, a color. But one can choose clothes that will favorably affect a human skin.

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